

Deprotonation of TPA on Cu(100)

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1 Introduction

Benzyl-carboxylic acids are widely used as synthons in the development of two-dimensional (2D) hetero-organic architectures on surfaces.^{1–5} On surfaces, carboxyl groups form different types of bonds including hydrogen bonds, carboxylate and metal–ligand bonds, giving rise to a variety of self-assembly mechanisms and structures. In this context, fundamental studies of benzyl-carboxylic acids adsorbed on metallic surfaces with a focus on the deprotonation reaction itself and also on its consequences on the stabilization of new structures have got renewed relevance.^{6–18}

Terephthalic Acid (TPA) is a prototype case of the above mentioned family of molecules and its adsorption and self-assembly properties, either alone^{7–13} or coadsorbed with different metallic atoms,^{3,19} have been studied on different surfaces. In particular, the TPA/Cu(100) system has been recognized as a model case to investigate the effects of deprotonation on molecular interactions and the resulting self-assembly structures,^{8,12} since the adsorbed molecule can assume either single or double deprotonation of its two carboxylic terminations. For any given coverage below one monolayer (ML), the TPA/Cu(100) system forms three different structural phases depending on the substrate temperature, namely α , β and γ , all of them with the molecules adsorbed flat on the surface. The α -phase is obtained by depositing molecules at low temperatures (LT, ~ 200 K) and is stable up to ~ 270 K, where it transforms into the β -phase. The latter is metastable and gradually transforms into the γ -phase at room temperature (RT), which is stable up to 400 K. It is well established that molecules in the γ -phase are arranged into a commensurate (3×3) superlattice composed of fully deprotonated molecules. The β -phase displays a $(9\sqrt{2} \times 2\sqrt{2})R45^\circ$ symmetry composed of a mix of fully deprotonated and semiprotonated molecules.¹² Although the α -phase is attributed to complete (*i.e.* protonated) TPA molecules, it has been scarcely investigated and its nature is not completely understood.

In the search for new methods of tailoring the formation of supramolecular networks on surfaces, we oriented our efforts to the investigation of surface alloys as a route for tuning molecule/surface interactions. Recently, we showed that the modification of a bare Cu(100) substrate by Sn alloying causes a strong reduction in the reactivity of a surface with respect to the carboxyl groups of TPA molecules. Furthermore, deprotonation is completely inhibited

on the $(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})R45^\circ$ reconstruction^{20,21} of the 0.5 ML Sn/Cu(100) phase (hereafter $3\sqrt{2}$) and the molecules form 2D sheets¹³ similar to those observed on a Au(111) substrate.⁷

In this work, we compare the adsorption and self-assembly properties of a TPA/Cu(100) system with those of TPA molecules adsorbed on a Cu(100) surface modified with a very small amount of predeposited Sn, which is shown to be sufficient for decreasing the Cu reactivity, while preserving its surface structure and symmetry. We thus performed a thorough study of the LT α -phase in the TPA/Cu(100) system by means of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM), X-ray Photoemission Spectroscopy (XPS), and Functional

Density Theory (DFT) calculations. In contrast with a previous report, we show that the α -phase is not a pure protonated phase, but a mix of protonated and semiprotonated TPA molecules. Finally, we compared the kinetics of the deprotonation reaction on the two substrates by tracking the amount of carboxylates with increasing temperature.

We show that the Cu(100) surface reactivity is larger than expected, being capable of catalyzing the partial deprotonation of TPA at a low temperature. Moreover, we propose a model where the semi-protonated molecules are incorporated in the α phase throughout the formation of single hydrogen bonds [OH \cdots O].

2 Methods

2.1 Experimental methods

Three independent ultrahigh vacuum systems were used to perform the experiments involved in this work. STM experiments were carried out at the Centro Atómico Bariloche, Bariloche, Argentina, while the synchrotron radiation (SR) XPS experiments were carried out at the ALOISA beam line^{22,23} of the ELETTRA synchrotron in Trieste, Italy. In addition, complementary XPS experiments were carried out in Bariloche using a SPECS system with monochromatized Al K α radiation in order to check the reproducibility. The three vacuum chambers have a base pressure in the low 10^{-10} mbar range.

The STM system is from Omicron Nanotechnology and is basically equipped with a variable-temperature STM (model AFM/STM VT 25 DRH), a LEED optics and a homemade ion gun for Ar⁺ sputtering. All the reported STM images were taken with W tips. Negative sample bias voltages correspond to the occupied-state images. Thermal drift was compensated during the measurements by applying the facility provided by the MATRIX software to control the STM.

In the STM chamber, the Cu(100) surfaces were prepared by cycles of sputtering at 1.5 keV and annealing at 770 K. Sn atoms were evaporated from a homemade Knudsen cell onto clean Cu(100) surfaces at a rate of 0.1 ML every 2.5 min approximately, as seen from the calibration obtained from the LEED patterns of the Sn/Cu(100) system aforementioned RT reconstructions.²⁰ The quality of the clean Cu(100) substrate and the $3\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction was checked by LEED.

The TPA molecules (Sigma Aldrich, 98% purity) were used as received. The molecules were evaporated from a resistively-heated boron nitride crucible at a rate of about 0.1 monolayer (ML) per minute. We define 1 ML as the surface coverage corresponding to the (3 \times 3) phase, that is, a molecular coverage of 1 TPA molecule per 9 Cu atoms in the top surface layer. In the STM chamber, the adsorption at LT was performed as follows. The substrate was cooled by means of a continuous-flow cryostat associated to the STM working with liquid nitrogen. Temperatures were measured using a Si diode located close to the sample on the clamp of a cold finger. At thermal equilibrium, the sample temperature is estimated to be 15 K higher than the Si diode reading. This correction is considered throughout this article. Once the sample reached the desired temperature (T_{STM}), it was disconnected from the cold finger and moved in front of the evaporator for TPA dosing. After the evaporation, the sample was connected again to the cold finger. From previous experiments,²⁴ we estimated a maximum temperature drift of 50 K. The preparation temperatures in the STM chamber are thus evaluated as ($T_{\text{prep}} = T_{\text{STM}} + 50$ K), which should be regarded as an upper value.

At ALOISA, the clean Cu(100) surface, the $\sqrt{3}\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction and the 3×3 phase, were verified using reflection high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED). SR-XPS data were obtained using a p-polarized X-ray beam at grazing incidence (about 4°). The spectra, taken with a photon energy of 655 eV, were measured in normal emission by means of a hemispherical electron analyser with an angular acceptance of 2° and an overall energy resolution of 300 meV. The Binding Energy (BE) scale of the analysed experimental spectra was calibrated by setting the BE position of the Cu $3p_{3/2}$ line to 75.0 eV. The experimental O1s XPS spectra were fitted with Voigt functions and Shirley-type backgrounds. A Lorentzian width of 0.15 eV was used in all cases. Four energy windows, centered on the regions of the Fermi edge and the Cu3p, C1s, and O1s core levels, were typically acquired by means of a 2D delay-line detector.²⁵ The evolution of the amount of carboxylates with increasing temperature was obtained by monitoring the corresponding O1s core level throughout sample annealing in a snapshot acquisition mode. This mode requires a lower kinetic energy resolution (600 meV) to collect the whole core level peak profile within a single shot (2 s) of the 2D detector. At ALOISA, the sample temperature was monitored by means of a thermocouple in direct contact with a Mo spacer below the sample.

2.2 Theoretical details

First-principles electronic structure calculations were performed within the DFT framework using the Quantum-espresso plane-wave code.²⁶ To take into account van der Waals interactions, we used the revised VV10 nonlocal exchange-correlation density functional.^{27,28} For the surface calculations, we used the slab method with four layers representing the surface and a vacuum size of ~ 10 Å. Except for the two lower layers that were kept fixed at the bulk distance, all the atoms in the cell were allowed to relax. Residual forces on the atoms after the geometric relaxation were smaller than 10^{-3} Ry a_0^{-1} . We used ultrasoft pseudopotentials with an energy cut-off of 30 Ry. Brillouin integrations were done using grids equivalent to $12 \times 12 \times 1$ for a $(\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})R45^\circ$ unit cell. Core-level shifts of the oxygen atoms are obtained as the total energy differences between the calculations performed with one of the oxygen atoms using a 1s core-hole pseudopotential.

3 Results

3.1 Characterization of the α -phase

A representative image of the TPA/Cu(100) α -phase prepared at a substrate temperature of 230 K is shown in Fig. 1, where the molecules are shown to grow by self-assembly into ribbons oriented at $\pm(9^\circ \pm 2^\circ)$ with respect to the $\langle 100 \rangle$ crystallographic directions of the substrate, which is in full agreement with the observations of Stepanow *et al.*⁸ Equivalent images were obtained at 180 K. A long wave-length modulation of molecular apparent height is a characteristic of the α -phase ribbons, as clearly shown in Fig. 1, which gives a striped appearance to the ribbon surfaces. The latter stripes (indicated by the blue dashed lines in the image) are oriented at $\pm(29^\circ \pm 2^\circ)$ with respect to the growth direction of the ribbons. The molecular network of the α phase has an intermolecular distance along the directions \vec{b}_1 or \vec{b}_2 of (7.3 ± 0.5) Å (see the inset of the figure); and the corresponding subtended angle

is ($78^\circ \pm 3^\circ$). The intermolecular distance along the growth direction of the α phase, ($\vec{b}_2 - \vec{b}_1$), is (9.5 ± 0.5) Å, which we observed to match very well with that of the 2D sheets formed by the complete protonated molecules on the $3\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction.¹³

In order to understand the chemical state of TPA in the α -phase, we compared the high resolution XPS of the O1s and C1s core levels with those measured in different phases and substrates at the same coverage of the sample shown in Fig. 1. In particular, we considered the (3×3) TPA/Cu(100) γ -phase and the LT phase of TPA on the Sn-alloyed Cu(100) surfaces. The O1s spectrum corresponding to the (3×3) phase, with a single peak at a BE of 531 eV (upper panel of Fig. 2), is a reference spectrum for terephthalates,^{11,12} corresponding to the film made only of fully deprotonated molecules.

In contrast, the O1s spectrum corresponding to the TPA on the $3\sqrt{2}$ -Sn/Cu(100) system (shown at the bottom of the middle panel of Fig. 2) can be considered as a reference spectrum for the 2D sheets of the protonated TPA molecules connected through the straight double [OH...H] bonds.¹³ This spectrum can be fitted with two main components separated by 1.31 eV,^{29,30} where the one at a lower BE (532.08 eV) is originated in the CO group, and that at a higher BE is originated in the OH group. In spite of having a similar spectral weight, the OH peak is systematically broader than the CO one, as previously reported for benzoic acid on Au(111).^{29,30} The spectrum of the TPA sheets grown on the $3\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction is very similar to that obtained for a multilayer grown at a low temperature (lower panel), apart from a rigid shift of 0.5 eV to lower BEs due to the surface screening by the metal substrate. The reduction in the Sn coverage from 0.5 to 0.1 ML does not cause qualitative changes in the line shapes beyond a slight increment of the shoulder at 531 eV, corresponding to the terephthalates.

The O1s peak of the α -phase looks significantly different from that of the TPA/ $3\sqrt{2}$ system. Apart from the prominent shoulder at ~ 531 eV, the O1s peak presents a dominant component at ~ 532.5 eV. The corresponding C1s spectrum presents a characteristic double peak in the BE region (284 to 285 eV) associated to the carbon atoms of the benzene rings, which is not seen in the other spectra. Thus, both the O1s and the C1s core-level spectra corresponding to the α -phase are not consistent with the common assumption of a fully protonated phase. In a previous work, Stepanow *et al.*⁸ fitted a O1s peak corresponding to the α -phase with two components, and associated the ribbons with a structure containing only protonated molecules forming double hydrogen bonds [OH...O]. However, a careful inspection of the O1s and C1s spectra presented by Stepanow *et al.*⁸ reveals that they are similar to the present ones of the α -phase, but they are smeared by a combination of poor resolution and a low signal to noise ratio (although the characteristic splitting of the benzene carbon peak can be easily recognized below the single peak fitting curve in Fig. 2 of ref. 8).

As a first attempt to rationalize the chemical state of TPA in the α -phase, we first tried to fit the O1s spectrum with a linear combination of a doublet corresponding to the protonated molecules (with a fixed intensity ratio) and one peak corresponding to a deprotonated TPA, as obtained from the reference spectra of the TPA/ $3\sqrt{2}$ -Sn/Cu(100) and (3×3)-TPA/Cu(100) phases, respectively. Even after relaxing the constraints on the peak width and position, this combination gives a clear mismatch with the measurements. The analysis of the difference spectrum reveals the need for extra components accounting for a residual intensity larger than 10%. We performed careful analysis and supplementary measurements in order to exclude any possible influence of either surface defects or contaminants. Furthermore, the STM images of this interface indicate that a large majority of the adsorbed

molecules are located in the α -ribbons. Therefore, the deprotonated contribution to the O1s spectrum should stem from the molecules in the molecular ribbons. We note that the C1s to O1s ratio of the peak areas (after correction by the cross-section) corresponds to the expected 1 to 2 stoichiometry. In addition, we verified that the line shapes of both the O1s and the C1s are highly reproducible on different Cu(100) samples, different experimental chambers and different spectroscopic instrumentation (see ESI,† Section S4), and therefore they must be related to the intrinsic properties of the TPA/Cu(100) system prepared at LT.

At a first glance, an additional contribution to the O1s line is clearly needed between the OH and the CO components at a BE of ~ 532.5 eV. We can exclude that this extra contribution may correspond to a carboxylate (COO^-) bound at undercoordinated sites. In fact, this component is shifted by ~ 1.5 eV to a higher BE from the carboxylate peak, whereas the coordination of the carboxylates to the Cu adatoms has been reported to yield a shift of only $+0.6$ eV in the case of the Fe–TPA metal–organic networks on Cu(100),³¹ and no shift for TPA on Cu(110).¹¹ Therefore, we tentatively assign this extra component to a OH peak shifted to a lower BE by ~ 0.8 eV.

3.2 Model for the carboxyl/carboxylate interaction in the α -phase

In order to determine the molecular configurations that can give rise to this extra OH peak, we performed DFT based simulations of the core-level shifts in the most plausible scenarios. We considered the following four possibilities: (I) paired carboxyl groups adsorbed at inequivalent adsorption sites of a surface, *i.e.* molecules in a different registry with a substrate; (II) unpaired carboxyl groups, *i.e.* not forming $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bonds with other carboxyls; (III) carboxyl groups interacting with adatoms or steps; (IV) carboxyl groups connected to a carboxylate by a single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond. We analysed these scenarios assuming a model based on the two interacting molecules adsorbed on the Cu(100) surface. In each case, after relaxation, we simulated the O1s core level shifts, taking as reference the corresponding one of the deprotonated TPA molecules in the 3×3 adsorption geometry. The O1s spectra were then simulated by convolution of the calculated discrete lines with a gaussian function.

The first scenario can be easily discarded because the variation of the adsorption site yields shifts in the OH and CO components within 0.1 eV. The scenario (II) is represented in Fig. 3(a and b), where each TPA molecule has one of the carboxyl groups forming a double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond, while the other one is unpaired, as indicated by yellow and blue circles, respectively. Fig. 3(c) compares the simulated peaks corresponding to the oxygen atoms involved in the double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond (orange line) with those of the unpaired carboxyl group (blue line). According to these simulations, the unpaired carboxyl group presents a significantly larger separation between the OH and CO components (2.2 eV) than the corresponding ones forming the double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond (1.51 eV). This is qualitatively in agreement with the experimental observations in the gas phase, where the carboxyl groups are reported to be separated by 2.1 eV,²⁹ compared with the 1.31 eV separation obtained

for the O1s spectra of the multilayer and the TPA/ $3\sqrt{2}$ surface alloy (Fig. 2). In addition, the unpaired OH peak would be shifted to a higher BE by ~ 0.3 eV, which is in the opposite direction of the required extra peak. The structural calculations reveal that there is a rotation of the unpaired carboxyl groups which brings the carbonyl (hydroxyl) closer (farther from) to the surface (see side view in Fig. 3(b)), which very likely contributes to the increase in the calculated energy separation. We can then discard the fact that the unpaired carboxyl groups contribute to the 532.5 eV peak.

To theoretically evaluate the possibility that a fraction of the molecules can interact with surface defects, we added two Cu ad-atoms close to one of the unpaired carboxyl groups which should give a good estimation of the chemical shifts due to the interaction with steps, ad-atoms, or step-kinks. We found a shift of ~ 0.15 eV to a lower energy with respect to those of the paired $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bonds that, although going in the desired direction, is quantitatively too small when compared to the required shift of -0.8 eV to account for the extra component at ~ 532.5 eV. We note that this conclusion is in excellent agreement with the STM measurements on the LT phase of TPA/Cu(100), which show only a few molecules decorating the surface steps.

Scenario (IV) is shown in Fig. 3(d and e), representing the possibility that a fraction of the TPA molecules in the α -phase is partially deprotonated. Starting from configuration (II) in Fig. 3(a), we deprotonated one of the paired carboxyl groups, otherwise connected with a double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond. After relaxing the geometry of this configuration, we found that the carboxyl/carboxylate interaction is stabilized by a single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond (indicated by the white circle in Fig. 3(d)). In this configuration, one of the O atoms of the carboxylate group is displaced downward, getting very close to the Cu atoms, while the other one is displaced slightly upward (see Fig. 3(e)). Remarkably, the intermolecular distance determined for the single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond is very similar to that obtained for the double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond of Fig. 3(a) (9.8 Å and 9.7 Å respectively). Fig. 3(f) compares the simulated O1s spectra of the carboxyl (red line) and carboxylate (green line) groups that are paired by a single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond. In spite of being chemically inequivalent, the O atoms of the carboxylate give rise to O1s peaks with similar BEs, which result in one single peak (green line) very close to the carboxylate position of the (3×3) phase (dotted line). In this case, the calculations predict a large chemical shift to the lower binding energy of the OH and CO components involved in the single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond. In particular, the OH peak is shifted by -0.5 eV, which is in reasonable agreement with the shift of -0.8 eV required to account for the extra component at 532.5 eV. The corresponding CO peak is shifted by 0.6 eV to a BE position very close to the carboxylate peak.

Therefore, from the analysis of the different configurations, we propose that the origin of the complex shape of the O1s line is the formation of single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bonds between the carboxylic and carboxylate groups facing one another. In order to test the proposed model, we built a fitting function with five peaks and applied it to the analysis of the experimental O1s spectra related to the α -phase of TPA/Cu(100) and to the LT phase of TPA on the Sn-alloyed surfaces. Four peaks account for the OH and the CO groups of the double and single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bonds (orange and red lines in Fig. 3(f)), and the fifth one for the carboxylate of the single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond (green line). According to this model, the areas of the three components associated to the single H bonds are correlated: the ratio of the area of the carboxylate peak, to the area of the CO peak and to the area of the OH peak must be 2 : 1 : 1. This condition was imposed to the fitting function.

Fig. 4 and Table 1 show the fitting results of the three O1s spectra shown in the middle panel of Fig. 2. We start the analysis from the O1s spectrum of the TPA/ $3\sqrt{2}$ -Sn/Cu(100) film (bottom) that can be fitted with two main components separated by 1.31 eV plus a minor component, $\sim 3\%$, associated with the carboxylates. Regarding the TPA film on the 0.1 ML-Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy (middle), the fitting results only show a small increment in the carboxylates. This finding indicates that a very low Sn amount is sufficient to eliminate the complexities from the O1s line of the α -phase (top) of TPA/Cu(100). However, the corresponding C1s line shows small peaks in addition to the two main ones associated to the fully protonated molecules. Clearly, these additional peaks are related to the component at 531 eV and, therefore, they should originate from the terephthalates adsorbed (with unknown configurations) on the surface.

For the α -phase of TPA/Cu(100), the peak shape of the proton $3\sqrt{2}$ CO and OH paired by the double bond is very close to the one used to fit the TPA/Sn/Cu(100) film, apart from a small decrease of 0.07 eV in the BE separation between the CO and OH peaks and a general width increase of ~ 0.25 eV. The latter is consistent with the expected small shifts (0.1–0.2 eV) caused by the different registries with the substrate and/or with the shift (0.3 eV) between the paired and unpaired carboxyl groups in the protonated state (Fig. 3(c)) due to dangling molecular terminations at the rim of the ribbons. The OH and CO peaks stemming from the protonated group paired to the deprotonated one by a single hydrogen bond display a slightly larger BE separation of ~ 1.5 eV, which is also in agreement with the trend predicted from the simulations. Notably, very similar values of the adjusted fitting parameters were obtained for the other two independently-prepared samples. Therefore, from our experimental O1s photoemission data set we conclude that the α -phase is composed of both protonated and partially deprotonated molecules.

We can now draw a model of the TPA ribbons of the α phase, where some semiprotonated molecules are intercalated between the protonated ones in the ribbons (see Fig. 5). The integrated areas, as obtained by the fittings, yield a ratio of 6.3 : 1 : 1 (75% : 12% : 12%) of the carboxylic groups forming the double H bonds (OH + CO) to the carboxylic groups involved in the single H bonds (OH + CO) and to the carboxylate groups (COO⁻) involved in the single H bonds. Each single bonded protonated-semiprotonated molecular pair contributes to the 2 groups directly involved in the single [OH \cdots O] bond and, additionally, to the other 2 carboxylic groups forming the double bonds. This implies that the population of the double bonded protonated-protonated pairs to the population of the single bonded protonated-semiprotonated pairs is 4.3 to 4. This means that about half of the molecules are involved in the single H bonds.

Regarding the C1s peak corresponding to the α phase, it presents a complex line shape with the five well resolved peaks at BE values of 284, 285, 286.8, 287.9 and 289.3 eV, as seen in Fig. 2. Due to the presence of many chemically inequivalent carbons in the five-peaks model, establishing a correlation between the observed peaks and the chemically inequivalent C atoms in the proposed carboxyl/carboxylate bond model is not easy. Notice that the single [OH \cdots O] bond implies a highly asymmetrical configuration for the C rings of the two involved molecules. For this reason, we limited the quantitative analysis to the O1s line shape. We will give, however, a qualitative explanation for the most prominent features in the C1s spectrum of the α phase. From a comparison of the C1s spectra obtained from the TPA adsorbed on the 0.1 ML-Sn/Cu(100) and $3\sqrt{2}$ surfaces, the peaks at 285 and 289.3 eV have to be associated with the contributions of the ring carbons and the carbons of the carboxyl groups of the complete molecules, respectively. Similarly, the peak at the lowest binding energy (284 eV) can be associated with the benzene carbons in the semiprotonated molecules. The shift to a lower BE by ~ 1 eV with respect to the case of the complete molecules is consistent with the case of trimesic acid on Cu(110), where a similar shift was reported.⁶ Regarding the peak at 286.8 eV, we attribute it to the contribution of the carboxylate groups in the partially deprotonated molecules. Finally, the origin of the peak at ~ 288 eV is less clear. We attribute this peak to the contribution of the protonated carboxylic groups involved in the single [OH \cdots O] bonds. This implies a shift of ~ 1 eV to a lower BE with respect to the contribution of the carboxylic groups involved in the double [OH \cdots O] bonds, which is comparable to the shift values obtained for the corresponding OH and CO peaks (see Table 1).

Looking at the spectral weight of each component, we observed some discrepancies (e.g. the peaks at 286.8 and 288.0 eV should have a similar intensity, while they yield a 1 : 2

ratio). In fact, the overall integrated intensity of the benzene-ring contributions at $BE \geq 286.2$ eV compared to that of the carboxylic contributions ($BE \leq 286.2$ eV), yields a ratio of 2.75 instead of 3. This means that the high BE side of the spectrum contains some contributions from the satellites of the benzene rings. In addition, the photoelectron diffraction effects due to the different adsorption sites of each carbon atom should also be taken into account. In conclusion, the relative intensity of the carbon peaks cannot be rationalized on the basis of simple stoichiometric arguments.

To gain a deeper understanding about the nature of the α phase, we calculated the adsorption energy of the two molecular configurations shown in Fig. 3. We found that the calculated energy gain associated to the formation of the double H bonds is 0.62 eV. Regarding the single H bonds, we found that they are unfavourable with respect to the double H bonds by 0.46 eV and, therefore, we conclude that they are stable at low temperatures. Thus, once a double H bond is formed, it will not break to form a single H bond. The partially protonated molecules should form first by deprotonation of the unpaired carboxylic groups and, then, they would incorporate in the α -phase by forming single H bonds.

3.3 Modification of the TPA self-assembly by Sn surface alloying

In our former study, we showed that TPA on a 0.5 ML-Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy aggregates into compact domains of protonated molecules in registry with the $3\sqrt{2}$ surface reconstruction.¹³ However, at coverages lower than ~ 0.1 ML, the Sn atoms are randomly distributed on the top surface layer,²⁴ which implies that TPA cannot adopt the same self-assembly mechanism and morphology of the $3\sqrt{2}$ case.

Fig. 6 compares the self-assembly morphology of the TPA molecules on the 0.1 ML-Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy with those observed on bare Cu(100). Both surfaces have the same molecular coverages and were prepared at the same substrate low temperature. It is evident that the 1D molecular chains are dominant on the modified substrate (Fig. 6(a)), whereas only a few of them are observed on the bare substrate. Although quite scattered in direction and length, the 1D chains display a regular intermolecular spacing of 9.5 ± 0.5 Å, which is a characteristic value of the TPA molecules connected through straight [OH \cdots O] double bonds,^{7,13} which is in agreement with the expectations drawn from the XPS analysis. Additionally, Sn alloying causes an observable increment in the amount of defects in the molecular arrangements. Notice that short straight chains and bent chains are frequent in the image. In the regions of the surface free of molecules, a lateral distribution of the embedded Sn atoms can be seen.

The effective inhibition of the single [OH \cdots O] bonds with such a low Sn amount may be rationalized in terms of the structural model in Fig. 3(d and e) and the local modification of the substrate structure. As discussed in the previous section, one of the two oxygen atoms of the carboxylate remains strongly bonded to a Cu atom, whereas the other displaces upwards to approximately the height of the C rings to form the single [OH \cdots O] bond. In the surface alloy, the embedded Sn atoms are displaced outwards by ~ 0.5 Å with respect to the outmost Cu layer,²¹ thus increasing the average vertical distance of any molecule standing above it as well. The increase in the vertical distance of the benzene rings with respect to the Cu atoms in the top surface layer, prevents the simultaneous formation of the required [OH \cdots O] and O–Cu bonds near a Sn atom. For similar reasons, the random lateral distribution of the Sn embedded atoms is responsible for the frequent bending and scattered orientation of the 1D segments.

The high corrugation of the surface, and therefore of the molecule–substrate potential, is even more effective in preventing the formation of a regular network of weak lateral H bonds between the molecules in the adjacent 1D chains. Thus, the variation in surface corrugation, associated to the randomly distributed low coverage Sn atoms, confine the TPA molecules into the percolating 1D chains of the double [OH⋯O] bonds.

3.4 Deprotonation as a function of temperature

The image in Fig. 7a, taken at 260 K, shows the intermediate stage of the irreversible $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ phase transition of the TPA/Cu(100) interface prepared at 220 K. Domains of the two phases are seen coexisting in the image. This transformation takes place in a narrow temperature range and a small temperature increment of 20 K is enough to transform the whole film into the β -phase. This is illustrated by the image in Fig. 7b, taken at 280 K, where only the 2D domains of the paired molecular rows aligned along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ crystallographic directions of the Cu(100) surface are seen.^{8,12}

The nucleation of the β -phase can be better appreciated in greater detail in the high resolution image in Fig. 7c, where the incipient β domains can be compared to the adjacent domains of the α -phase. The β -phase appears to be formed by the fragmentation of the α -phase domains into short segments of paired rows that are the seeds of the β -phase. This molecular re-organization, due to an azimuthal reorientation of the TPA molecules,¹² also leads to the disappearance of the long-wavelength modulation of the α phase ribbons. In this regard, we notice that the variation in the apparent molecular height of the α -phase is smoothly changing across multiple molecules, as emphasized in the Z-profiles shown in Fig. 7d. This indicates that the long-wavelength modulation cannot be directly associated with some specific structural feature of the single [OH⋯O] bonds, instead it is likely due to the different registry of the molecules with the substrate lattice.

The corresponding evolution of the O1s and C1s photoemission spectra across the $\alpha \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \gamma$ phase transformations is shown in Fig. 8. In order to prevent kinetic effects due to thermally activated reactions, the sample was heated for 20 s at the indicated temperature just before measuring XPS. First of all, the integrated intensities of both the C1s and O1s spectra were found to be practically constant in the considered temperature range, indicating a negligible molecular desorption from the α to they-phase. We then note that the XPS changes are very small from 228 K to 273 K, while a sharp rise in the O1s carboxylate component at 531 eV takes place between 273 K and 293 K. The heating experiment ended at 381 K with a typical spectra in the 3×3 phase.

Finally, we compared the kinetics of the deprotonation reaction on the bare Cu(100) surface and on the 0.1 ML-Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy. To this aim, we measured O1s spectra in real time during heating at a 40 K min^{-1} rate in a snapshot acquisition mode on the two surfaces. The corresponding temperature variation in the relative weight of the carboxylate component is shown in Fig. 9. The general slope of the carboxylate temperature dependence on the bare Cu(100) surface resembles those previously reported for other carboxylic acids on a Cu(100) surface,^{32,33} where a steep rise is observed close to RT. In this case, however, the deprotonation curve does not have a steady slope, but it presents well defined features. The amount of carboxylates remains practically constant from 230 K up to ~ 290 K, after which it starts to increase steeply. From the comparison of the STM images (Fig. 7) and the XPS spectra (Fig. 8), we associate the initial plateau to the activation barrier increase related to the formation of the α -phase, and the drastic change of the slope observed at 290 K to the transformation of the α -phase into the β phase. Similarly, we attribute the sharp step edge at ~ 320

K to the stabilization of the β phase. After the occurrence of a narrow plateau associated with the thermal stability of the β phase,¹² the amount of carboxylates monotonically increases up to ~ 380 K, where all the adsorbed molecules become deprotonated. This third and last plateau reflects the formation of the fully deprotonated (3×3) phase. We remark that the transition temperatures from one structural phase to the next one derived from this experiment are higher than those derived from the variable-temperature STM experiments and steady-temperature XPS analysis (see Fig. 7). This is due to the fast heating/rate used in the snapshot experiment combined with the mounting setup of the sample at ALOISA: the thermocouple is not in direct contact with the sample, but with a Mo spacer below the sample, thus determining a heat-load impedance during the variable temperature experiments. Nonetheless, the occurrence of the well defined plateaus in the carboxylate curves allows us to unequivocally identify the different TPA phases.

In the case of the Sn-alloyed surface, the increase of carboxylates sets in already at the lowest considered temperature (see Fig. 9). The increase of the carboxylates now displays an almost steady slope up to the full conversion into a deprotonated phase at 380 K, thus smearing both the LT plateau and the intermediate one corresponding to the β -phase on the bare Cu(100) surface. This strongly suggests the existence of a multiplicity of activation energy barriers for the deprotonation due to the intrinsic disorder of the Sn-alloyed surface. In particular, we attribute the observed increase in carboxylates in the low-temperature range (from 230 to ~ 290 K) to the occurrence of the unpaired and poorly coordinated carboxylic groups (e.g. associated with the frequent bending of the 1D chains, see Fig. 6(a)) since they should have a lower activation barrier than the carboxylic groups involved in the well-formed $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bonds. Finally, the amount of carboxylates on the surface alloy saturates at the same temperature (375–385 K) as in the case of the Cu(100) surface. However, the saturation value is only $\sim 80\%$ of the initial amount of the molecules. This is due to the opening of the molecular desorption channel at 350 K (see the inset). Indeed, about 20% of the molecules desorbes from the surface in the temperature range of 350 and 375 K. We note that the temperature range where the molecular desorption takes place is the same as that observed in the TPA/ $3\sqrt{2}$ case,¹³ which suggests that the desorbed molecules are complete molecules coming from the regions of the surface with a lower local reactivity due to a higher local density of Sn atoms.

4 Conclusions

We showed that both the O1s and the C1s photoemission peaks of the LT α -phase of TPA on Cu(100) are not compatible with a molecular layer made of fully protonated TPA molecules connected through double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bonds, as reported in former models.⁸ We proved the presence of a significant fraction of deprotonated molecules by comparing the XPS spectra recorded on the fully deprotonated γ -phase and the films grown on the Sn-alloyed surfaces that prevent molecular deprotonation. By means of DFT based simulation of the O1s core level photoemission, we demonstrated that the most plausible scenario is described by the formation of a single hydrogen bond $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ between the carboxylic group of a protonated TPA with the carboxylate group of a semiprotonated TPA. In this model, the molecular structure of the observed ribbons is similar to that of the 2D sheets formed by the protonated TPA molecules on inert surfaces such as Au(111) and on the $3\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction of the Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy, but with an approximately one to one population of the single bonded protonated-semiprotonated TPA pairs to the double bonded protonated–protonated pairs. A comparative analysis of the energetics related to the formation of single

and double H bonds on the Cu(100) surface indicates that the semiprotonated molecules are generated by the deprotonation of the unpaired carboxylic groups. Once a semiprotonated molecule is formed, it is incorporated in the α -phase by forming a single H bond. This novel motif of hydrogen bonding could be exploited in supramolecular architectures based on two carboxylic-acid species with different deprotonation probabilities.³⁴ Finally, by monitoring the kinetics of the deprotonation reaction, we showed that the intercalation of the semiprotonated molecules into a regular network of H bonds does not weaken the activation barrier for further deprotonation on the Cu(100) surface, whereas it takes place at a lower temperature of ~ 50 K for the isolated or poorly coordinated protonated molecules on the 0.1 ML-Sn/Cu(100) passivated surface.

Figures and Tables

Figure1 STM image of the LT α -phase of TPA/Cu(100) at a molecular coverage of 0.4 ML.

Figure 2 Comparison of the representative O1s and C1s photoemission spectra of the TPA films adsorbed on different substrates. Upper panel: Typical spectra of the (3×3) -TPA/Cu(100) phase, as obtained after annealing at 400 K. Middle panel: representative spectra of the TPA films obtained by depositing ~ 0.4 ML of TPA at ~ 230 K on the Cu(100) surface and two Sn/Cu(100) alloys with an increasing Sn content: top curve, the TPA/Cu(100) LT α -phase, with a coverage determined from the spectrum of (0.38 ± 0.05) ; middle curve, TPA adsorbed on the 0.1 ML Sn/Cu(100) alloyed surface, with a coverage of (0.38 ± 0.05) ; bottom curve, TPA adsorbed on the 0.5 ML Sn/Cu(100) alloyed surface (the $3\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction), with a coverage of (0.34 ± 0.05) . Lower panel: XPS spectra obtained from a multilayer of the TPA molecules grown on the Cu(100) surface kept at ± 230 K. Notice that the latter O1s spectrum shows a small component at 536.8 eV, which we attribute to a shake-up satellite; consistently, this component is observed also in the films grown on the passivated Sn/Cu(100) alloyed surfaces.

Figure 3 Upper panel: Top (a) and side view (b) of the relaxed structure of the two TPA molecules forming a double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond. (c) Blue and orange lines correspond to the simulated O1s core-level photoemission spectra of the structure shown in (a). Lower panel: Top (d) and side view (e) of the relaxed structure of the two TPA molecules connected through a single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond. (f) The red and green lines correspond to the simulated O1s core-level spectra related to the single $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ bond (white circle in (d)). The orange line corresponding to a double $[\text{OH}\cdots\text{O}]$ shown in (c) is also included in (f). The simulated spectrum obtained for a deprotonated TPA molecule in the (3×3) adsorption geometry is included in (c) and (f) for comparison (dotted line).

Figure 4 Quantitative analysis of the O1s spectra already shown in Fig. 2. Bottom: TPA adsorbed on the $3\sqrt{2}$ reconstruction of the Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy. Middle: TPA adsorbed on a 0.1 ML Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy. Top: TPA adsorbed on the bare Cu(100) substrate. The optimized parameter values are summarized in Table 1. Orange components: OH and CO peaks of the double [OH...O] bond. Red components: OH and CO peaks of the single [OH...O] bond. Green component: carboxylate.

Figure 5

Model for the α -phase of the TPA/Cu(100) system. The ribbons are composed of both the complete and semiprotonated molecules forming an arrangement similar to that of the 2D sheets formed by the protonated TPA molecules. On average, half of the molecules are involved in single [OH...O] bonds (dashed circle). The spatial distribution of the single H bonds in the depicted ribbon is arbitrary.

Figure 6

STM images taken at 130 K with -2 V/20 pA. (a) TPA molecules deposited on the 0.1 ML-Sn/Cu(100) surface alloy held at 180 K. Molecular coverage (0.33 ± 0.05) ML. The inset shows with enhanced contrast a region devoid of molecules in between the molecular chains, where the embedded Sn atoms can be discriminated. (b) TPA molecules deposited on Cu(100) also held at 180 K. The inset shows a zoomed image of the ribbons where the modulation stripes are seen more clearly. Coverage: (0.33 ± 0.05) ML.

Figure 7

STM images illustrating the irreversible structural transition from the α -phase into the β phase induced by temperature. (a) The surface prepared at ~ 220 K after increasing the substrate temperature to 260 K. Image taken at the same temperature with (-2 V/500 pA). (b) The same sample but at 280 K (-2 V/200 pA). The β -phase is observed. (c) STM image taken at 260 K (-2 V/500 pA). The observed modulation stripes are characteristic of the α phase. The colored lines indicate the growth direction. (d) Height profiles along three contiguous chains of the molecules corresponding to the colored lines drawn in panel (c).

Figure 8

Evolution of the O1s and C1s photoemission spectra (left and right panels, respectively) as a function of temperature of a 0.38 ML coverage of TPA deposited at ~ 230 K. See text for experimental details of the heating procedure. The small extra component (blue shaded curve, 7% of the total intensity) in the O1s spectrum of the γ -phase effectively accounts for the observed asymmetry of the carboxylate peak, a characteristic of the terephthalates also observed on Cu(110).

Figure 9

Fraction of carboxylates relative to the total intensity of the initial O1s peaks, as a function of substrate temperature, for both the bare Cu(100) and the 0.1 ML-SnCu(100) surfaces. The arrows indicate the thermal stability range of the α , β and γ phases as discussed in the text. See text for details. The inset shows the total area of the O1s peak normalized with respect to the total intensity of the O1s peak obtained from each sample.

Interface	O1s	Double [OH...O]		Single [OH...O]		Carboxylate
		CO	OH	CO	OH	
α phase	E_B	532.15	+1.24	531.06	+1.48	530.99
	W_G	1.30	1.61	0.75	0.90	0.99
	Area	36.0%	39.1%	5.7%	6.2%	12.0%
TPA/0.1 ML Sn	E_B	532.20	+1.31			531.12
	W_G	1.15	1.38			1.07
	Area	43%	47%			10%
TPA/ $3\sqrt{2}$	E_B	532.08	+1.31			530.70
	W_G	1.09	1.31			0.97
	Area	46%	50%			3%

Table 1: Main parameter values obtained from the fittings of the O1s spectra shown in [Fig. 4](#). E_B and W_G are expressed in eV.

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